

Methods to prevent the duplication of efforts in projects and networks

Deliverable 2.7

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Executive summary of the project

Organic Farming Innovations Network Europe – OH-FINE has a duration of 48 months, starting from the 1st of November 2024, and is funded by the European Union in the framework of Horizon Europe, the European Union's Research and Innovation Programme 2021-2027, and by SERI, the Swiss Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation. The project is coordinated by the Institute of Natural Resources and Agrobiology of Salamanca (IRNASA), which is part of the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC). The project focusses in empowering European farmers by advancing and sharing sustainable organic farming knowledge and solutions that align with farmer capabilities, consumer demands, and evolving food market trends. The project involves 18 partners from 9 countries.

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DRAFT

1. Introduction

This document has been prepared as part of WP2 of the OH-FINE project (Project set up, needs assessment and baseline establishment), in particular task 2.7: “Developing specific methods to prevent the duplication of efforts observed in ongoing or previously completed projects and networks”. On the other hand, this activity has some points complementary with other tasks of the project, in particular 5.8 and 6.8: Collaboration with other projects. In addition, task 10.6, 11.6 and 12.6 also include collaboration, knowledge exchange and joint initiatives with various particular Horizon Europe funded projects. Therefore, the first phases of the proposed methodology include a screening to detect related ongoing projects and a coordination mechanism to foster possible collaborations. By tackling tasks together, it's easier for all partners to get work completed and avoid duplicating efforts.

2. Proposed methodology: overview and features

2.1. Overview

The proposed methodology aims to prevent duplication of efforts and to facilitate cooperation with other European projects and projects implemented by Operational Groups by combining strategic analysis, knowledge management, and reuse of results. Although the user manual with the guidelines is adapted to the specific needs and subject matter of the OH-FINE project, this methodology has a flexible outline and structure, with the idea that it can be reused in the context of other projects.

The general outline of the methodology has been designed using information obtained through Copilot Enterprise, a generative AI based on the GPT-4 model. Its capabilities have been leveraged to design a structured approach to prevent duplication of efforts. The instructions given to the AI have been clear and oriented to obtain a basic outline of steps to follow that is agile and easy to implement. At no point were specific project details or sensitive data provided to the AI. Once the general outline with the 5 working phases was obtained, each phase was reviewed in detail, studying whether it was appropriate for the purpose of the methodology and analysing the possibilities for improvement. In addition, all sources used by the AI were checked to verify their origin and credibility. Ultimately, the document has been modified, extended and manually adapted to the needs of European projects in general, and OH-FINE in particular.

Although this document is intended as a guide for OH-FINE partners and contains very specific details regarding the structure and activities of OH-FINE, we believe that the general structure is flexible enough to be used in other projects.

The proposed methodology takes its name, SCOPE, from the 5 phases that make it up: Scan, Connect, Organise, Prevent and Evaluate. They are summarised in the following table:

Table 1

Phase	Objective	When
Scan	Identify existing projects and networks related to the project scope.	Each six months for new Operational Groups and European projects (Task 5.8 – 6.8 participants). Whenever an activity that is likely to be done in collaboration is initiated*
Connect	Establish links with similar or complementary projects	After identifying potential collaborations
Organise	Systematize information for reuse	During execution
Prevent	Integrate mechanisms to prevent duplication	Before delivering results
Evaluate	Measure the effectiveness and adjust accordingly.	Every year

Table 1. General summary of the 5 phases of the proposed methodology.

* For the OH-FINE project, details are specified in the full explanation of this phase.

In order to facilitate the adoption of the methodology by all partners, a webinar will be organised once the methodology is established. The steps of the process were explained and doubts were discussed. In addition, the seminar will be recorded for later consultation. Additionally, annual meetings will be established between the main responsible of the tasks involved (CSIC as project coordinator, OFISET and TEAGASC) to follow-up the fulfilment of the collaboration objectives.

On the other hand, it should be noted that the proposed methodology aims to be realistic and applicable. Although many more indicators and verification processes could be included to improve results and evaluation, we consider it more appropriate to establish a flexible, simple procedure that does not involve an excessive workload. In this way, we ensure that all partners will internalise it and apply it on a regular basis.

2.2. Responsibilities at different stages

The SCOPE methodology will be applied in the project to ensure that duplication is prevented, and synergies are identified and leveraged.

This list details who should apply the methodology and when:

- Each partner participating in task 5.8 and 6.8 (Collaboration with EIP-OG): OFISET, CSIC, TEAGASC, WULS, ITP-CHIRPAN, LAMMC, FIBL-AT, EV ILVO. Every year review new Operational Groups and other local call projects in your country.
- OFISET, TEAGASC and CSIC (as task leaders and project coordinator): every year, review new Horizon Europe, LIFE and other European Projects
- Each partner in its own institution could talk directly to colleagues involved in related projects.
- Each partner when attending networking activities and events can identify synergies and duplicities with other projects.

Members who scan projects shall, in the event of identifying possible duplications or synergies in any tasks, will inform those members who are involved in these activities.

Some examples of specific tasks in which collaborations can be found are as follows: seminars, workshop, meeting, field trials, field trial demonstration, cross visit, dissemination material or any other activity that is likely to be done in collaboration. See *Section 3.2. Phase 2: Connect – Establishing Synergies and Strategic Links* for more information.

2.3. Centralization process

The centralization process involves using a shared database where partners can log identified synergies. This ensures that all partners are aware of existing synergies and can avoid duplications within the project.

Details on the database are provided in the description of each phase of the methodology (Table 3 for information on projects with identified synergies and Table 4 for collaborations carried out). The fields proposed in the database could be adapted to suit the needs of each project.

3. Guideline for partners: step by step

3.1. Phase 1: SCAN – Identification of existing projects and networks

The Scan phase involves identifying existing projects and networks that may be relevant to the project, in order to avoid duplication and leverage synergies. This is achieved through a systematic review of previous projects using platforms like CORDIS, OpenAIRE, Horizon Dashboard and national projects database

This prevents other partners from repeating the same search or proposing already identified synergies.

Steps of SCAN phase:

1. Define the search focus

Before searching, clarify:

- What is the topic of your task/project?
- What type of results do you need (data, reports, tools, training materials, etc.)?
- What is the geographical or sectoral scope (regional, national, European / livestock, cropping system, etc.)?

Examples of keywords that can be used for searching: organic farming, arable crops, livestock, knowledge exchange, conversion, multi-actor, AKIS, innovation, co-creation, cross-fertilisation, empowering farmers, dissemination, spreading of organic farming, thematic network, farming learning community, cross visit, field demonstration

2. Analyse synergies already identified

Check the shared excel. Maybe a partner has already identified a project that could be interesting for your objective.

3. Search in your institution

Identify possible projects in which your institution is involved, locate your colleagues involved.

4. Search in key sources

Use these platforms to find similar projects:

Table 2

Platform	What to search for	Link
CORDIS	EU-funded projects (Horizon, FP7, etc.)	https://cordis.europa.eu
OpenAIRE	Open publications and data from projects	https://www.openaire.eu
EU Funding & Tenders Portal	Beneficiaries, results, synergies	https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding
Zenodo	Repository of reusable results	https://zenodo.org
Organic e-prints	open-access archive for research results	https://orgprints.org/
EU- Farm Book	Repository of research results	https://www.eufarmbook.eu/en
Organic Farm Knowledge	Dissemination materials related to organic farming	https://organic-farmknowledge.org/
EU CAP Network	EIP-AGRI projects, practice abstracts, Operational Groups, Horizon Europe	https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/index_en

Table 2. List of platforms that can be used to search for similar projects

5. Analyse the project found

Study the objectives and the activities that will be carried out to detect if there are any overlaps or potential collaborations. You can obtain this information from their publications and websites, by attending presentation events, or by contacting the coordinator or another project partner directly.

6. Record the results in the shared excel

Whenever you identify synergies, fill in the following fields in the excel:

Table 3

Excel field	Description	Example
Call	Call that has funded the project (if known)	HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01-20
Project Name	Name of the project	Organic Advice Network
Website	Website (if exists) or, for example, link to project information in Cordis	https://www.organicadvicenetwork.eu/
Duration	If known, duration of the project	2024-2028
Geographical area	In the drop-down menu you can choose whether it is worldwide, European, local to one of the OH-FINE countries, or 'other'.	European
¿OH-FINE partner involved in the project?	If any of the institutions of the OH-FINE consortium are involved (they are probably different researchers, but they may know each other)	FIBL-CH, INAGRO, BIOSELENA
Type of Synergy/duplicity detected (e.g., data reuse, collaboration, joint field trials visit, workshop...)	Indicate possible synergies or duplications (e.g.: cross visit manual that we can reuse) and possible collaborations to suggest	They are going to develop a platform, practice materials and policy recommendations focused on organic advisors Collaboration suggested: present a poster in Spanish forum and participate in parallel workshop about international projects
Partner(s) who identified	Enter your name/institution. This way, if in the future another partner wants to collaborate with the same project, they can ask you first to know where we stand.	CSIC
Direct contact?	Indicate if you know anyone involved in the project or if you have already made contact with someone, and how	Two meetings held with Claire morelle, project coordinator; Contacted by mail to invite to the forum (waiting answer)
Data contact	Indicate data contact	xxx@xxx.com

Table 3: Guide for filling in the fields with information on the projects identified in the database

Helpful Tips

- Don't limit yourself to identical projects: look for complementary ones too.
- Use varied keywords and synonyms.
- If unsure whether something is already registered, check the Excel before searching. Note that it is possible to establish more than one collaboration with the same project but, in any case, it is advisable to first speak with the partner who has previously

established contact with the project to find out exactly what has been agreed and how the collaboration has worked.

3.2. Phase 2: Connect – Establishing Synergies and Strategic Links

The objective is to establish links and synergies with similar or complementary projects, networks, and stakeholders to enhance collaboration, avoid fragmentation, and build on existing knowledge.

If you are seeking a specific collaboration (e.g., you are organising a field demonstration and want to see if you can visit a trial in your region for another project), you can complete the previous phase (SCAN) or use the database to see if there is a previously identified project that may be useful to you.

Before connecting, take a moment to reflect on the following questions:

1. Identify relevant actors and networks

Before reaching out, clarify:

- Are you looking for collaboration, knowledge exchange, organize joint activities?
- What thematic or geographical scope is most relevant?

2. Map and analyse connections

Take advantage of the search for synergies in the previous section and review the shared database. Perhaps another partner has identified a project that might be interesting for you to connect with.

3. Establish synergies

Once actors are identified, explore possible synergies:

- Contact coordinators of similar projects to propose collaboration.
- Join or initiate thematic working groups or communities of practice.
- Share your project's goals and explore mutual benefits (e.g., joint events, shared tools, co-publications).

Ideas for possible collaborations for OH-FINE

- Joint field demonstrations
- Collaborative field trials
- Organise workshop, seminars and meetings together
- Develop joint policy briefs
- Invite as speaker to the forum
- Establish knowledge-exchange platforms
- Resources and information sharing, for example knowledge needs detected
- Develop joint dissemination material

- Participate in training courses
- Participate in focus groups
- Visit field trials of other projects during cross visits

4. Document connections in the shared Excel

When you start a collaboration, fill in the following fields in excel

Table 4

Excel field	Description	Example
Check list (First column in the data base)	This field is designed to track the objectives we have committed to in the Grant Agreement. Mark it only when the collaboration has become effective (leave it blank at the stage of identifying synergies). Choose the type of project from the drop down list	Horizon
OH-FINE COLLABORATION 1: Title	Indicate the type of collaboration that has taken place.	Dissemination material with practical recommendations for conversion to organic
OH-FINE COLLABORATION 1: When? (Workshop date, field trial visit date...)	Indicate the date of the event	Published in November 2025
OH-FINE COLLABORATION 2: Title	Please note that several collaborations can be made on the same project. In case of new collaborations, please add new columns to write the data.	
OH-FINE COLLABORATION 2: When? (Workshop date, field trial visit date...)	Indicate the name of the second collaboration	
Comments	If there is anything else worth recording, please list it here.	Our project officer has insisted that we should find some way to collaborate in the design of the platform.

Table 4: Guide for filling in the fields with information on collaboration with other projects in the database

Helpful Tips

- Be proactive: don't wait for others to reach out.
- Use personal networks and social media to identify hidden opportunities.

- Keep communication clear and professional—represent the project well.
- Track follow-ups and outcomes of each connection.

3.3. Phase 3: Organize – Structuring Knowledge for Reuse

The objective is to systematize the collected information and results to facilitate their reuse, ensure accessibility, and promote interoperability across projects and platforms. The OH-FINE Data Management Plan (Deliverable 1.2) sets out the basis for applying Open Science principles and making project data FAIR (see 3. below). This will facilitate making the results accessible and reduce the risk of duplication in the future. Furthermore, it is important to disseminate information on the web and social media.

Some of the main points to take into account when structuring data to facilitate its reuse are summarised here:

1. Create a structured repository

Organize all relevant outputs and resources in a centralized, accessible location:

- Choose platforms that support open access and long-term storage (In our project, OH-FINE collection in Zenodo and Organic e-prints).
- Classify materials by type: datasets, reports, tools, training materials, etc.
- Ensure proper version control and documentation.

2. Apply common ontologies and taxonomies

Use standardized vocabularies to ensure consistency and interoperability:

- Adopt EU-recognized taxonomies such as EUROVOC or Agrovoc.
- Tag resources with thematic keywords and metadata.
- Align with sector-specific standards where applicable.

3. Implement FAIR principles

Ensure that all data and results are:

- Findable: Use persistent identifiers (e.g., DOIs), searchable metadata.
- Accessible: Ensure open access or clear access conditions.
- Interoperable: Use standard formats and vocabularies.
- Reusable: Provide licenses, documentation, and provenance information.

4. Communicate and disseminate

In addition to publication in repositories, it is important to disseminate the results and activities of the project effectively, as researchers often use social media and web searches to find relevant information from other projects.

In this regard, it is very important that all partners send information and photographs of the activities and material produced to those responsible for communication (SEAE) and dissemination (FIBL-CH). All this information will be published on the project's website and social media, and we will also try to include it on the social media of the participating institutions.

3.4. Phase 4: Prevent – Avoiding Duplication through Smart Monitoring

The objective is to integrate duplication prevention mechanisms into project management by using intelligent tools and structured assessments to ensure originality, complementarity, and added value.

With regard to duplication, it is considered that in some cases this does not necessarily have to be 'negative'. For example, many projects organise training courses on the management of herbaceous crops in organic farming. Depending on the project, the target audience may be different (farmers, advisors, scientists, etc.). The geographical area in which it is organised may also vary, as may the specific focus on a particular type of crop or climate. In this case, we do not consider this duplication to be something to be avoided.

In the case of OH-FINE, two types of actions have been identified in which it is advisable to avoid duplication:

- Digital platform
- Dissemination materials

In the case of the digital platform, an exhaustive scan has been carried out using advanced search tools and AI, in addition to gathering information from partners. This ensures that the tool developed provides new features that complement what already exists.

For the development of the architecture of the OH-FINE ICT Tool, different data sources were considered. This component aggregates high value content from leading European initiatives and platforms in organic farming (See deliverable 4.1. OH-FINE Platform for more information). Once our platform has been developed, if we identify projects that include the development of a platform or DSS among their objectives, we will contact them to explore possible collaborations.

In the case of outreach materials, it shall be ensured that these cover any information gaps that have not yet been covered by existing materials.

3.5. Phase 5: Evaluate – Measuring Impact and Driving Improvement

The objective is to measure the effectiveness of the proposed methodology in terms of reuse, collaboration, and efficiency, and adjust practices based on evidence and feedback to ensure continuous improvement.

As already mentioned, we have aimed to be realistic in our methodological proposal and do not consider it feasible to establish more indicators or KPIs than those already included in our Grant Agreement.

The methodology will be evaluated during the annual meetings between those responsible for the related tasks and the project coordinator (TEAGASC, OFISET and CSIC).

An interim evaluation will be carried out for all partners to verify whether they are encountering problems in identifying synergies, what the obstacles to collaboration are, and whether they have any proposals for improving the methodology, especially with regard to coordination with other partners.

4. Infographic summary

The following figure provides a quick guide for all partners on the steps they should take to seek synergies and establish collaborations (Phases Scan and Connect).

Figure 1

Figure 1. Quick guide for partners

5. Summary Table: Recurring Cycle of Actions - SCOPE

Methodology

Table 5

When	What to Do	SCOPE Phase	Objective
At the start of each task that is likely to be done in collaboration	Perform a quick scan and establish connections	Scan, Connect	Establish synergies and avoid duplications
During execution	Organize resources and document their origin	Organize	Facilitate traceability and reuse
Before delivering results	Prevent duplication by verifying existing resources	Prevent	Avoid delivering redundant results
Every year	Conduct self-evaluation and provide feedback	Evaluate	Continuously improve and coordinate efforts

Table 5. Summary table with the objectives and timelines for each phase of the proposed methodology